

N-m-Tolyl-p-methoxybenzohydroxamic Acid—A New Reagent for the Solvent Extraction of Copper(II)

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Copper(II) forms a green coloured chloroform extractable complex with *N-m-tolyl-p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid* (TMBHA). The absorption maximum of the complex is at 510 nm. The method is simple, rapid and employed for the determination of copper in some of its common alloys such as brass, bronze and german silver. A characterisation of solid complex of copper with TMBHA is also discussed

SEVERAL solvent extraction methods for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of copper are known and a number of chelating agents¹⁻⁷ have been used for the purpose. However, these methods have some limitations, such as incomplete extraction³, longer extraction time⁴ and use of synergetic extractions. 4-5-Benzyl-1-para-chlorophenyl-5-phenyl-2,4-isodithiobiuret (BPPTB)⁸ and diphenylcarbazone⁹ have been used for the extraction of copper, but the complexes were found to be unstable. Copper(II) has been recently extracted with quinoline-2-aldehyde thiosemicarbazone (QAT)¹⁰. Molar absorptivity for this method is reasonably good ($\epsilon = 1.33 \times 10^4 \text{ dm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$) but colour stability is only 30 min. Oximes are also widely used for the extraction of copper¹¹. 2'-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime (HMMCO) and 2'-hydroxy-3'-bromo-4-methoxy-5'-methylchalcone oxime (HBMMCO) have earlier been synthesised and employed in the laboratory for the extraction of copper¹².

HMMCO^{12,13} and structurally related *N-m-tolyl-p-methoxybenzohydroxamic acid* (TMBHA)^{14,15} are well established analytical reagents. The extraction studies of Nb^V, Ta^V and Ti^{IV} with these reagents have been reported¹⁶⁻¹⁸ from this laboratory. The studies revealed that TMBHA is comparatively more sensitive and selective reagent for extractive spectrophotometric determination of metals. The stability constant values of the metal complexes have shown that TMBHA forms more extractable complexes than HMMCO. Keeping this in view, the extraction study with TMBHA was continued. The present communication reports the extraction of Cu^{II} with TMBHA.

Copper(II) forms green coloured chloroform extractable complex with TMBHA at 4.5 pH which absorbs maximum at 510 nm. It is possible to extract copper in presence of most of the commonly associated ions. The method is simple, rapid and can be employed for the determination of copper in

some of its common alloys. In addition to the extraction behaviour of Cu^{II} with TMBHA, we also describe here the characterisation of solid metal complex by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurements and IR spectra.

Experimental

Copper(II) solution was prepared by dissolving copper hydroxide, obtained from CuSO₄·5H₂O (AnalaR) in perchloric acid and was standardised¹⁹. TMBHA was synthesised and purified by the earlier methods²⁰.

Procedure: An aliquot of solution containing about 8 μg of copper(II) was adjusted to pH 4.5 and the total volume of the aqueous phase was made upto 10 ml. The solution was extracted with $5 \times 10^{-4} \text{ M}$ TMBHA (10 ml) in chloroform for 10 min. The absorbance of the green chloroform extract was measured at 510 nm against the reagent blank. The amount of metal extracted was computed from appropriate calibration curve.

Results and Discussion

Spectral properties of Cu^{II}—TMBHA complex: Cu^{II} forms a green coloured chloroform extractable complex with TMBHA. Spectral properties of this complex are reported in Table I. The data for copper(II) complexes with other reagents^{12,21-23} are also given for comparison.

Effect of variables: Extraction of Cu^{II} commences from pH 2.5 and reaches a maximum at pH 4.5. A twenty-fold excess of the reagent is sufficient for quantitative extraction of the metal. Amongst the several solvents tried (*viz.* benzene, toluene, chloroform, carbon tetrachloride, isoamyl alcohol and isobutanol), chloroform was found to give maximum absorbance and sharp peak. The extraction was quantitative in 10 min.

Effect of foreign ions: The interferences of several ions were studied. The tolerance limit was

TABLE 1—SPECTRAL DATA OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES IN CHLOROFORM

Compd.	λ_{max}	Molar extinction coefficient $dm^3 mol^{-1} cm^{-1}$	Beer's law range $\mu g Cu/ml$	Sandell's sensitivity $\mu g Cu/cm^2$
Cu ^{II} -TMBHA ^a	510	8.50×10^4	0.04–1.2	0.000 8
Cu ^{II} -HMMCO ^b	375	1.09×10^4	0.50–12.5	0.005 8
Cu ^{II} -phenanthraquinone-monothiosemicarbazone ^c	540	1.16×10^4	0.25–3.5	0.005 0
Cu ^{II} - <i>N</i> -(4-methoxy-phenyl)- α -thiopicolinamide ^d	440	8.00×10^3	0.50–5.0	0.008 0
Cu ^{II} - <i>N</i> -(4-methyl-phenyl)- α -thiopicolinamide ^d	430	6.60×10^3	0.50–5.0	0.010 0
Cu ^{II} - <i>O</i> -mercaptoacetoacetanilide ^e	630	5.57×10^3	0.10–9.0	0.010 0

^aPresent work. ^bRef. 12. ^cRef. 21. ^dRef. 22. ^eRef. 23.

set as the amount of foreign ion needed to cause $\pm 1\%$ error in the recovery of the metal ion. The ions studied for the interference include alkali metals, alkaline earth metals, Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, Co^{II}, Ni^{II}, Zn^{II}, Hg^{II}, V^V, Mo^V, W^{VI}, La^{III}, U^{VI}, Th^{IV}, Pb^{II}, Cd^{II}, Sn^{II}, Nb^V, Ta^V, Ti^{IV}, Cr^{VI} and Ce^{IV}. Copper can be extracted quantitatively without any serious interference of most of these ions. The ions which interfere strongly are Fe^{II}, Fe^{III}, U^{VI}, V^V, Co^{II} and Ce^{IV}. V^V, Fe^{II} and Fe^{III} could be masked with tartaric acid. Ni^{II} could be tolerated up to five-fold excess of copper. Most of the anions including EDTA, fluoride, thiocyanate and cyanide did not interfere.

Determination of copper in alloys: Copper could be determined quantitatively in different alloys like brass (Cu, 61.25; Zn, 38.75%), bronze (Cu, 87.26; Sn, 8.42; Pb, 1.96; Zn, 1.20%), german silver (Cu, 56.0; Zn, 20.0; Ni, 8.0; Pb, 7.0; Fe, 5.0%). The relative standard deviation obtained from ten determinations was $\pm 0.45\%$.

reagent TMBHA is more suitable and sensitive for the extractive spectrophotometric determination of copper(II). The method is rapid, selective and applicable to some common alloys of copper.

Structure of Cu^{II}-TMBHA complex: The study of the solid complex of copper(II) with TMBHA was done to confirm the proposed composition and structure of the complex. The elemental analysis indicates metal to ligand ratio of 1 : 2 which is the same as that obtained by solvent extraction technique in the present study. The magnetic moment value (1.86 B.M.) corresponds to 3d⁹ configuration of Cu^{II} with one unpaired electron. The electronic spectra of the complex show two shoulders at 430 and 590 nm which may be attributed to d-d transitions in the complex. This suggests square-planar or distorted octahedral geometry for Cu^{II}T-MBHA complex. The results are in good agreement with the findings of earlier workers^{20,21}. The ir spectra of the complex was compared with that of TMBHA²⁰. The spectra showed three prominent peaks at 1 600 (C=O stretch), 1 080

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF COPPER(II) COMPLEXES

Compd.	Yastimirskii's method			Leden's method		
	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$	$\log K_1$	$\log K_2$	$\log \beta_2$
Cu ^{II} -TMBHA	5.02	4.88	9.90	4.92	4.73	9.65
Cu ^{II} -HMMCO	3.45	3.03	6.48	3.29	3.02	6.31
Cu ^{II} - <i>N</i> -(4-methoxy-phenyl)- α -thiopicolinamide	5.21	4.65	9.86	4.96	3.64	8.60
Cu ^{II} - <i>N</i> -(4-methyl-phenyl)- α -thiopicolinamide	4.81	4.33	9.14	4.45	3.66	8.11

Composition of the extractable complex and stability constants: The 1 : 2 (M—L) stoichiometry of the extractable complex was observed by Job's method²⁴, mole-ratio method²⁵ and slope-ratio method²⁶. The conditional stepwise stability constants of the complex ($\log k_1$ and $\log k_2$) were evaluated by Yastimirskii method^{27,28} and Leden's method²⁹. Table 2 shows that the overall stability constants ($\log \beta_2$) obtained by the two methods agree well with each other. The stability constant values for other reagents are also given in Table 2 for comparison.

The comparative data from Tables 1 and 2 show that TMBHA forms stable complex with copper and the reagent is spectrophotometrically more sensitive as compared to other reagents. Thus, the present

(N—O stretch) and 445 cm⁻¹ (Cu—O stretch). The band at 3 100 cm⁻¹ (O—H stretch) disappeared on complexation. These observations indicate the coordination of the ligand through carbonyl oxygen.

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